

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable D5.3 Deliver all obligations

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordination and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Description of deliverable in the grant agreement: “Deliver all obligations under the grant agreement and provide the European Commission with necessary reports and data”

1.1 Project aim

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platform (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan and its integrated roadmap – with a long-term perspective, beyond the period of the project.

2 DELIVER ALL OBLIGATIONS UNDER THE GRANT AGREEMENT AND PROVIDE THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION WITH NECESSARY REPORTS AND DATA

This is a Horizon Europe project where the grant agreement gives an asset of obligations and commitments to be fulfilled. This deliverable will summarise them.

2.1 Summary of the work

The overarching objective of the project has been achieved. The project successfully grew and maintained a robust, inclusive, and long-term stakeholder network that will continue to support the implementation of the SET Plan and its integrated roadmap well beyond the project's timeframe.

Through inclusive and transparent stakeholder engagement, the project fostered alignment on the strategic direction of CCUS in Europe. Coordination between ETIP ZEP and IWG9 was operationalised efficiently, with joint quarterly ZEP Advisory Councils and IWG9 Plenaries bringing together over 130 stakeholders per session, including industry, academia, civil society, national governments, and EU institutions.

Key achievements include:

- **Seamless Coordination of Governance Structures:** Joint strategic decision-making was carried out through the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary. Coordination culminated in a revised ZEP governance structure adopted in December 2023, ensuring long-term organisational strength and continuity.
- **Influence on Policy and Regulation:** The project aligned stakeholders and provided input on major EU policy initiatives, including the Net-Zero Industry Act, the Carbon Removal Certification Framework, and the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy. Numerous consultations were answered, reinforcing the project's role as the official advisor to the European Union.
- **Thought Leadership and Technical Contributions:** The project produced key reports on CCS and biodiversity, CO₂ transport by ship, public perception of CCS, and CCUS supply chains. It also launched new Working Groups on critical technical areas such as Carbon Dioxide Removals and Finance, reflecting the evolving needs of the CCUS ecosystem.
- **Support to CCS Project Deployment:** A major milestone was the launch of the **Projects Network** in January 2024 in Rotterdam – a new ZEP workstream dedicated to accelerating CCS deployment. The inaugural event gathered 125 stakeholders and received strong feedback. A second Projects Network event in Bologna, Italy took place on 24-25 June 2025, co-hosted with ENI and Snam, and sponsored by Heidelberg Materials Italy, Mitsubishi Heavy Industries EMEA, Bellona and KNCC.
- **Institutional Transition and Long-Term Continuity:** From 1 July 2024, ZEP Communications ASBL assumed full responsibility for the ZEP and IWG9 secretariats, ensuring seamless continuation of work.

2.2 Deliverables

All deliverables from the grant agreement have been delivered.

No.	Deliverable name	Type	Lead partner	Support partner	Delivered?
D1.1.	Work programme, dissemination and communication plan	R	CCSA		yes
D1.2.	Engagement programme	DEC	CCSA		yes
D1.3.	Review of the ETIP/IWG and opportunities to increase future impacts	DEC	CCSA	SINTEF	yes
D1.4.	Review of the IWG9 R&I activities and targets	DEC	SINTEF	ZEP-C	yes
D1.5.	Recommendations regarding Certificates for Carbon Dioxide Removals	R	CCSA		yes
D1.6.	Recommendations focusing on Social Sciences and Humanities expertise	R	CCSA		yes
D2.1.	Recommendations on CCUS R&I priorities for Horizon Europe work programme	R	SINTEF	CCSA	yes
D2.2.	Annual progress reviews and recommendations on the 8 R&I activities	R	SINTEF	ZEP-C	a) yes b) yes c) yes
D2.3.	Insights on EU and national support instruments for CCUS R&I and deployment	R	CCSA	SINTEF	yes
D2.4.	Report on key enablers and hurdles for CCS/CCU projects, focus on public perception	R	CCSA	SINTEF	yes
D2.5.	Active support and recommendations to the European Commission CCUS Forum	DEC	CCSA		a) yes b) yes
D2.6.	Report on CDR, article 6 of the Paris agreement and the needed regulatory framework	R	CCSA		yes
D3.1.	Outreach programmes and briefings with European institutions and Member States	DEC	ZEP-C		yes
D3.2.	Develop the website	DEC	CCSA		yes
D3.3.	Disseminate the knowledge developed through external workshop events.	DEC	ZEP-C		yes

No.	Deliverable name	Type	Lead partner	Support partner	Delivered?
D3.4.	Present outputs and recommendations at SET Plan Steering Group events, other EC initiatives, etc.	DEC	ZEP-C	SINTEF	yes
D3.5.	Develop presentation materials and give presentations at external conferences	R	ZEP-C		yes
D4.1.	Disseminate reports and recommendations to Member States	R	ZEP-C		a) yes b) yes
D4.2.	Input from national governments on the focus and outputs from the project	DEC	CCSA		yes
D4.3.	Support from national governments on delivery of the Implementation Plan	DEC	CCSA		yes
D5.1.	Project Management Plan	OTHER	CCSA	SINTEF	a) yes b) yes
D5.2.	Data management plan	R	CCSA	SINTEF	yes
D5.3.	All obligations under the grant agreement	OTHER	SINTEF	ZEP-C	yes
D5.4.	Outputs for the work packages as requested by the ZEP AC and IWG9 Plenary	OTHER	ZEP-C		yes

2.3 Milestones

All milestones from the grant agreement have been achieved:

Milestone	Milestone reached
M1 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary	14.09.2022
M2 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary	14.12.2022
M3 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary	22.03.2023
M4 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary	14.06.2023
M5 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary	13.09.2023
M6 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary	13.12.2023
M7 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary	20.03.2024
M8 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary	19.06.2024
M9 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary	11.09.2024

M10 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary	04.12.2024
M11 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary	12.03.2025
M12 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary	11.06.2025

2.4 Progress of the project

The project progress has been followed up by monthly project meetings, and by informing ZEP and IWG9 about the grant status in their quarterly meetings.

The project has had three reporting periods of 12 months each.